

Resolved: Open practices make science better

Presented at the Researcher to Reader (R2R) 2023: Debate Session

*Authors and Presenters (in order of their presentation): **Rick Anderson** (University Librarian, Brigham Young University), **Malvika Sharan** (Senior Researcher - The Alan Turing Institute, and Co-Director - Open Life Science), **Steven Heffner** (Managing Director, Publications, IEEE), **Catriona J. Maccallum** (Director of Open Science at Hindawi Publishing), **Karin Wulf** (Beatrice and Julio Mario Santo Domingo Director and Librarian, John Carter Brown Library and Professor of History, Brown University)*

Video recording of the debate is available on Researcher to Reader's YouTube Channel:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jgfFfqCjo5M>.

Please cite this document as described on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7687845>, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7687845](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7687845).

Introduction

Credit: Rick Anderson

At the 2023 Researcher to Reader Conference in London, I moderated a formal debate of the proposition **Resolved: Open practices make science better**. The debaters were Steven Heffner (Managing Director, Publications at IEEE) and Karin Wulf (Director and Librarian at the John Carter Brown Library, Brown University), both arguing against, and Catriona MacCallum (Director of Open Science, Hindawi Publishing) and Malvika Sharan (Senior Researcher, Open Research at the Alan Turing Institute), both arguing in favour.

The opening statements and responses are provided below.

Opening Statements in Favour of the Proposition

Credits: Malvika Sharan, Catriona Maccallum

Open practices actively facilitate transparent, participatory, collaborative and ethical research by enabling the involvement of diverse stakeholders, including those impacted by their outcomes. Through transparent reporting, openness reinforces ethical standards, scientific rigour and quality in research by opening up underlying data, research methods and processes for independent scrutiny – building accountability and public trust.

Open science is a discipline that encompasses various areas of research and promotes open ways of working, enabling equitable and inclusive approaches at all stages. For instance, open source software, open data standards, open education, citizen science and open access utilise open practices to enhance the diversity of knowledge and knowledge producers – leading to greater cognitive justice. Despite the diverse sets of goals and challenges across different sectors, like academia, industry, government and the public sector - and different disciplines, including the arts, humanities and social sciences - openness is the common thread that defines scholarship and advances the mission of making knowledge freely available for global access. Irrespective of domain-specific challenges, open practices contribute to (i) producing public goods like publications, tools, and practices; (ii) encouraging greater collaboration among researchers from

different disciplines, and (iii) broadening the diversity of knowledge-producing actors (Arza, V., & Fressoli, M. (2017). [Systematising benefits of open science practices](#)).

Transparency and openness have proven to improve research integrity and accelerate scientific and research through replication and reproduction efforts. The worldwide response to the covid pandemic has shown just how impactful open practice in action looks on a global scale. Although stimulated by the urgency of tackling the crisis, it compelled the government, funders, researchers and members of society to come together, gather all resources they needed, create systems of knowledge exchange and prioritise human lives and public safety above all. To that end, UNESCO mobilised over 122 countries to promote open science and made a joint appeal to reinforce international cooperation to [lift patents for vaccine equity](#).

For equity to become a reality, it is important to explore: *“to whom does knowledge belong? Who benefits from the production and circulation of research outcomes? Who gets to participate in the production processes? and, in what ways can research be used to increase the agency of more people over knowledge production?”*. I am quoting [Contextualizing Openness: Situating Open Science](#) (edited by Leslie Chan, Angela Okune, Rebecca Hillyer, Denisse Albornoz, and Alejandro Posada), where the research team presents the Open and Collaborative Science in Development (OCSDNet) Manifesto, which thoughtfully and carefully emphasises – that open practices: *enable a **knowledge commons**; recognise **cognitive justice**; practise **situated openness**; advocate individual’s **right to research**; foster **equitable collaboration**; incentivise **inclusive infrastructures**; and use knowledge as a **pathway to sustainable development**, equipping every individual to improve the well-being of our society and planet.*

“Tragedy of Commons”, a phenomenon popularised by Biologist [Garrett Hardin in 1968](#), is a common argument we continue to hear in the 21st century. Ironically, this was precisely what Elinor Ostrom debunked in the 80s and 90s. In her book, [Governing the Commons](#), she highlights Hardin's quote: *"Ruin is the destination toward which all men rush, each pursuing his own best interest in a society that believes in the freedom of the common"*. She states the limitations where - (1) Hardin focused on ‘access’ without ‘governance’; (2) he assumed little or no communication between the people involved; (3) he postulated that people act only in their immediate self-interest; and (4) he offered only two solutions to correct the tragedy—privatisation or government intervention. I will add the fifth point (5) his analysis of a "pasture open to all" and "herders" or as he emphasises "all men", operate in the absence of the rest of the world, without intersectional perspectives, solidarity or collective actions. Rather than assuming that open to all means, accessible or beneficial to all, open practices work towards democratising access to resources, which in our case are funding, infrastructure, and support such as at individual, institutional, geographical and political levels, that diverse stakeholders need to address multi-fold challenges concerning them. Open practices are about access and reuse, rather than open for exploitation or opening up without considering the ethical implications. Openness builds shared agency and operates to dismantle power imbalance in research culture as well as infrastructure for co-creating solutions that are useful for everyone.

The consequence of a narrow, selective or partial view can fuel an ‘anti-commons’ or ‘anti-trust’ agenda, leading to excessive intellectual property rights or over-patenting, resulting in privatisation, vendor lock-in, commercial exploitation and underuse of scientific resources. What is knowledge good for, if it only makes the rich richer and does nothing to benefit the broader society? Isn't it highly unethical, and in fact, a violation of human rights when systems of knowledge choose not to address the exploitation of labour and extraction of knowledge from already marginalised and disadvantaged communities? What role has

western notions of meritocracy and scholarship - and western notions of publishing and gatekeeping - had in fueling this inequity?

Since the release of the [Budapest Open Access Initiative](#) 20 years ago, we have seen a social, economic and technical shift toward openness. However, the unwillingness of the research community, including publishers, to adopt the technological and cultural advances in the infrastructure has blocked us from taking full advantage of what openness can offer. At the heart of this cultural impasse is a financial and reputational reward system that locks in the economic and academic capital of those who already benefit from the system. Already privileged stakeholders have been self-selected to win in the existing system and vulnerable members advocating for new systems of open scholarship are ejected before their careers can get off the ground. Publishers - commercial and not-for-profit – as well as institutions gain financially from brands, legacy evaluation criteria and opaque publishing workflows that are no longer fit for purpose. New innovative and open publishing start-ups and platforms cannot get a foothold in the ‘market’ or are swallowed up by the oligopoly of existing publishers. There is a wholesale recognition of this challenge encapsulated in the [UNESCO Recommendations for Open Science](#). It is primarily funders who are leading and driving the change required – Wellcome Trust, the EU Commission, UKRI and most recently the OSTP. These innovative funders are now transforming the policy landscape to encourage, enforce and invest in open practices easing the routes to innovation that will serve not just science but all of society.

Openness is not a panacea or a target in and of itself. It is an instrument, a tool, that we can use to improve research practice. Edge arguments against open practices minimise the complex, nuanced and situated openness and try to explain them through simplistic, reductionist and highly unrealistic metaphors created to glorify the notion of a ‘[free rider](#)’ – under the guise of academic freedom. Rather than upskilling researchers in best practices and transparent processes, the closed elitist academic system expects researchers to uphold perverse incentives and assessment processes. Justification of restricted access and closed collaboration often comes from the assumption that researchers inherently want to participate in the academic competition and race to climb up on the leaderboard even though participation in such an unfair system is restricted to only those who are able to pay the access and contribution cost. Knowledge sharing is not a competition or zero-sum game – we don’t lose by sharing them, in fact, systemic progress depends on the knowledge of those who came before. Open practices allow us to expose and dismantle the restrictive, non-inclusive and discriminatory status quo in the socio-technical infrastructure of research and help find ways of increasing trust, developing norms of reciprocity, or crafting new rules with all stakeholders of research.

As an open science educator, I can't finish my argument without mentioning [FAIR principles](#) that provide a framework to make all research objects Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable, while maintaining privacy and protection where necessary. It is encouraged to be co-applied with the [CARE principles](#), leading to Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility and Ethics. The CARE principle was developed in 2018 in Botswana as a tool for responsible data governance through leadership by people who are producers and owners of the data. Developed by Indigenous and allied researchers and practitioners, CARE demands the decolonisation of practices and technology and safeguarding of vulnerable communities by protecting their knowledge such as [land data](#) and [indigenous languages](#) against exploitation.

Radical collaboration and interdisciplinarity have allowed us to witness the emergence of good practices such as FAIR and CARE principles. Open sharing has also led to breakthroughs in research - be it the example of “big team science” of the human genome project, the distributed model of Wikipedia, the countless codebase upon which data science continues to thrive or the fact that the [COVID vaccines were made](#)

[available in record time](#). Openness has proven itself time and time again for facilitating responsible research resulting in outcomes that are independently scrutinised, reused and improved upon.

In an era, where we are facing an unprecedented number of global challenges ranging from the pandemic, climate change, natural disasters and even wars, we need to acknowledge open practices as our duty as researchers and members of society. I urge you to choose openness – more precisely, ‘transparency, interdisciplinarity and collaboration’ – to become ‘researchers without borders’. Let’s use our privilege and position to reexamine access and assessment [for greater participation] in research so that stakeholders with a wider range of backgrounds, identities, expertise and domain knowledge are valued and given the opportunities to participate in research – improving research quality, reducing harm and sharing benefits.

Opening Statements against the Proposition

Credits: Steven Heffner, Karin Wulf

This debate is framed as whether “open practices make science better.”

It seems inconceivable that anyone here would argue otherwise. Openness, transparency, collaboration, and cooperation – these are essential to the research enterprise. A full exchange of data and ideas in a discursive space free from bias and corruption would be a difficult vision to refute, and that debate would have little real-world practicality.

We cannot, however, be debating these values in the abstract; rather, we must be debating whether “open science” – which has come to mean a set of monolithic mandates for making published research freely available under certain terms – makes science better. Is “openness” as it is currently being implemented good for science? Here we think there is room for healthy disagreement.

We submit that we’re on a path to openness that has fundamental flaws, ones that will significantly damage scientific progress. We further submit these practices will damage our global polity by ignoring the broader context of academic activity and sidelining, if not silencing, lines of inquiry fundamental to progress.

From our vantage we see 4 major problems with “open” as currently conceived and implemented.

1. It fails to support and sustain a diverse and high-efficiency scholarly communications system.
2. It fails to safeguard the incentive structure around high-quality research, instead creating mechanisms in the marketplace that are incongruent with the objective of truth seeking..
3. It fails to account for the sharp differentials among disciplines in how research is conducted, prepared, and shared – to the great detriment of our social fabric and civic health.
4. It fails to understand how the research enterprise unfolded over the last 100+ years and demands we prioritise free consumption above all else.

While we see other challenges with “open science”, we will elaborate on these four.

1. We start with alterations in funding. The movement from the reader- or user-pays models of scholarly publishing will remove a significant amount of money from the ecosystem.

In the current subscription-based environment, upwards of 40% of publisher revenue comes from institutions that have no research output at all. These read-only customers are primarily (but not exclusively) corporate customers from R&D intensive sectors—some of the largest companies in the world in pharma, biotech, healthcare delivery, tech, aerospace, and energy. In a fully open access, author-pays

world, these institutions will not be paying in. They'll be getting a free ride. Regardless of whether one thinks this is fair, this money will no longer contribute to the ecosystem.

There's an assumption in open movements that the entire infrastructure is a given—metadata standards, linking structures, archiving services, abstracting, indexing, bibliometrics, fraud-detection, etc. These functions were primarily built by and continue to be funded by scholarly publishers. Innovation in the space, too, depends on continued investment to develop new ways to move faster, share data, encourage collaboration, identify misconduct, and enforce norms.

Is there a better way to fund this shared ecosystem and drive progress? Perhaps, but what's certain is that the current trajectory naively and recklessly defunds the enterprise we all believe in, with no conception of how to replace those resources.

2. This leads to our second point, regarding misaligned incentives. Open access mandates as they are currently being implemented set up perverse incentives that will impede and corrupt the scientific endeavour.

The goal of research is to advance human knowledge. Scholarly communication facilitates this truth-seeking by bringing the best information forward for the widest possible group of scholars to synthesise and build upon.

Vital to that dissemination of scholarly output is a disinterest in anything other than quality process and output. Publishers must be agnostic about the source of the knowledge-generation, the wealth or political ideology of the funders, and the conclusions of the research. They need to provide a fair, rigorous, and trustworthy application of peer review and an even-handed and useful presentation, the objective being quality science for the community of scholars and practitioners.

Publishers and other intermediaries are incentivized in this endeavour by the approbation of the consumers. When they compete in this marketplace, publishers have incentive to produce more rigorously vetted content in a form suited for maximum utility.

In the open access environment, the incentives for high-quality output fade. Driving revenue is a simple volume calculation: publish more papers regardless of quality. And we've already seen that there are plenty of commercial concerns willing to publish as many articles as academia can pay for. And make no mistake: These publishers have willing accomplices in academia at all levels, which continues to incentivize output at a furious pace—Publish or perish!

But this is not a question of whom to blame—academia's promiscuous output of underwhelmingly mediocre papers or commercial publishers' voracious appetite for APCs. Neither of these innate characteristics (ambition and avarice) can be fixed. Rather, as in all human systems, they need to be mitigated. So, it ought to be a question, rather, of how a system minimises the temptations of these groups to realise their worst instincts and, instead, incentivizes the creation of good science and the rejection of junk.

The current vision for open access does neither of these things, but rather solidifies the unholy alliance of these pernicious behaviours. The result will be (and already is) a scholarly literature flooded with mediocre science – or worse, destructive misinformation – produced and published at scale with fewer tools from a de-funded discovery and curation industry.

3. Current policy and mandates around open practices fail to account for the sharp differentials among disciplines in how research is conducted, prepared, and shared. This insensitivity to the diversity of academic practices gives priority to the biggest volume and most well-funded fields, rather than allowing a critical assessment of social needs to drive our practices.

This debate is framed around “open science,” but it is really about research more broadly, and only in some particular places does science include the arts, humanities, and social sciences. The major drivers of openness are narrow: biomedical science in particular, and not even foundational fields such as mathematics much less social sciences such as economics.

But as much as we need medicine and what technology brings us, we need the humanities as much – if not more. History, for example, is a vital perspective for understanding our experience. Autocrats know this. It is no accident that powerful entities are attacking historical knowledge and research; history is empowering.

“Open science” ignores the low-cost, highly distributed way that humanities research is funded, and the intensive, highly skilled editing and preparation required to create carefully articulated work – labour supplied mostly by nonprofit publishers. Humanists expect their work to serve the public good, and they commit tirelessly to public engagement in popular print, broadcast, and social media – vital messages built from the expert work they circulate and publish among a community of experts. The mandates for openness make this work, which underpins all other inquiries, substantially harder if not impossible to pursue.

It seems the height of folly that we even consider creating entirely new, more complex, and more costly systems with less editorial mediation and necessary labour to replace journals in the humanities and social sciences that cost libraries mere 100s of dollars annually.

We cannot allow these critical fields of study to become the collateral damage of a primarily biomedical research ideology. These fields are not incidental; they are fundamental!

4. “Open science” mandates ignore all other urgent research issues and prioritise free consumption above all other virtues in the research enterprise.

“Open Science” conceives all issues as related to free and immediate online access. Essentially “Open Science” prioritises easy consumption of research as primary. We see this differently.

The research enterprise in the West is the product of two historical moments: the late 19th century disciplinary commitments to empirical methods, and the mid-20th century expansion of funding for science largely as part of national security – both primarily first-world phenomena.

In a world where we need to think about global cooperation in facing the major crises of our time – the imperilled climate, imperilled democracy – shouldn’t we pull ourselves out of the constraints of that first-world Western context? Isn’t it, in fact, imperative to empower researchers around the world, and particularly in the Global South, for the global public good? But instead the late 20th century global economy prioritised cheap consumption, and often to the detriment of workers in the global south. The open movement likewise emphasises cheap consumption of research and, through its author-pays models, makes it difficult or impossible for researchers in the global south to participate.

In short, the calls for “open” are well intentioned. They ask for things that, in theory, we should all want. However, in practice this movement is driving an inversion of the very things we profess to value. Is free access for theoretically needy users so valuable that we’re willing to:

- Decimate a funded system of interconnectivity?
- Sacrifice a centuries-old method of values alignment around quality scholarly output?
- Cede a robust interdisciplinary understanding of human progress to the best-funded fields?
- Further complicate diverse global participation in the solutions to our common problems?

We, in opposition to the proposal, say NO.

Response

Credits: Catriona Maccallum

With respect to our honourable colleagues, their 4 arguments depend on a series of fundamental fallacies. They mistake a business model *for* open access and a business model of open access with the practices and principles that make up Open Science practices – and then they conflate the ability for others to access, discover, reuse and contribute to research with torrid notions of ‘consumption’. And in relation to the deep inequities and lack of support for open infrastructure - where do we even begin... Thank God for funders - open practices wouldn’t have gotten off the ground if it were up to researchers, scholarly societies and publishers....

They stated that “Vital to [the] dissemination of scholarly output is a disinterest in anything other than quality” And yet, they fail to recognise that the perverse incentives they deplore have been fueled by a lack of transparency and a deeply inequitable system of gatekeeping in both research and publishing practices. The system they want to keep intact for the sake of ‘quality’ has created the hypercompetitive culture that is causing the problem - a lack of willingness to share information in case you get scooped, the black box of peer review where bias is rife, the gatekeeping of knowledge that bars anyone who is different from having an influence on the system. Indeed, it is now so bad that misconduct has become almost commonplace and authors are willing to pay editors and reviewers to manipulate the peer review system - whether in open access or subscription journals.

The publishing system they extole has been propped up by privileged and profitable brands – run as much by not-for-profit societies as well as commercial publishers – brands that have locked in the supremacy of the global north both academically and financially. There is already more than enough money in the system to help fund open practices - it just requires redistribution. The irony of their argument is that it is actually increased openness that will help drive down costs and mitigate against the problems. It is the willingness to share data about what works and what doesn’t work that has helped expose the lack of scholarship and research integrity in this so-called academic meritocracy. Making your work open makes it available for public scrutiny - and not just for academic peers. It makes us accountable to everyone in society.

Moreover, they make the argument that the Humanities should somehow be exempt from such open practices? To refer back to Ostrom, they believe the humanities are falling prey to the tragedy of the commons and should therefore be a privileged edge case, ring-fenced off from the rest of science. And the specific argument they put forward is because it is cheaper to publish and distribute that type of research and that the editing done by publishers is so skilled? If, as they say, “humanists expect their work to serve the public good” then why don’t they make their work a public good by opening it up to everyone. Do the humanities not have rigorous scholarship and methodologies that should also be shared and independently scrutinised. Are humanities and history not subject to the same biases and inequities created by a lack of transparency that have been exposed in biomedicine? And why on earth should biomedicine alone reap the

benefits of open science? I agree wholeheartedly that the humanities are important - and way too important to be closed off.

Members of the audience - how can you even think of opposing the motion...

Response

Credits: Steven Heffner, Karin Wulf

In the strict time allotted, We'll respond to two points in our colleagues' opening statement, and then return to the primary point of ours.

First, our colleagues ask "to whom does knowledge belong?" Invoking vaccines, and the pandemic crisis, they call for "the production and circulation of scientific knowledge" to benefit everyone through expanded participation in both the process and fruits of research.

Yet the very framing of the question betrays the problem here. Knowledge does not exist independent of either contexts or resources. It literally does not grow on trees, so even if we could shift the ownership of the land and access to the orchard, knowledge isn't an apple. It's a complex and often ephemeral human product shaped by a set of institutional and other relationships.

Second, our colleagues lament that while there has been a "social, economic, and technical shift to open," researchers and publishers have been resistant. They are—we are, I guess—"block[ing] us from taking full advantage of what openness can offer."

But let us be clear. We are not "Team No." We are not "Team Luddite" – though with better historical contextualising we'd all use that analogy better and maybe in the best sense we are in fact Luddites, advocating for fair labour practices and for shared resources. But I digress, and I promised not to! We are not Team Elite Greedy Hoarders of Research, either. And neither are we Team Clueless Unthinking Legacy Publishing Addicted Leming Researchers.

Move Fast and Break Things is very Elon Musk 1.0 – even if Elon hasn't moved on from that mode, we have. Moving at Deliberate Pace and Building, Repairing, Recycling, and Repurposing is what the world has learned to value again.

Yesterday we heard a chemist raise many of the same questions we raised about Open Access, from a researcher perspective: about equity for researchers, about the lack of consultation with researchers, about the priorities of researchers. Calling for a return to the values that drove people into science and for research communities –communities of people who care about producing research for the public good– to come together in the first place.

So here we are not arguing against "openness" and "accessibility" which are inarguably good things but rather what "open access" has wrought. We are Team Context. Team Deliberate Process. Team Collaborative Research Practices for the Public Good. I don't know a single scholar who doesn't want to make their work more accessible.

As a historian, I have long lamented the ways that monolithic OA policies are making it harder, more expensive and more time consuming to just publish good humanities research –at the very moment when the world is in the direst need of history.

At the very moment when universities are cutting humanities faculty and majors, when politicians around the world are making it harder, even illegal, to teach evidence-based history, when democracies are threatened and autocrats are ascendant on a tide of historical misinformation and myth.

At this very moment when in fact we need *more* humanities research for a rising tide of crises that are not technical or technological, but social and political, and we are still having to argue about OA policies that are not fit for research diversity –of discipline and geography and researcher profile. Recent studies of the US and Canada make this plain. In Canada, of the 562 historians who earned a PhD between 2016 and 2022 only 10% secured tenure-track employment. We will not have historians to fund at this point.

You may ask what this has to do with OA. It has everything to do with driving agendas that are meant for one problem and generalise to the whole of the research ecosystem, with an overwhelming focus on hard and life sciences above all else.

We have prioritised free general consumption of one thing– expert published research–over all else. Let us reconsider how that value competes with other things of abiding value for humanity which the group assembled here is committed to advance.

Closing

Credit: Rick Anderson

At the beginning of the debate, the audience was polled to determine how many were in favour of the proposition and how many opposed; the result of this initial poll (97 respondents) was 87% in favour, 13% opposed. The debate then began, with a ten-minute opening statement provided by each side and then a three-minute response from each side. Discussion with the audience followed. After the discussion period, the audience was polled again; the result of the second poll (91 respondents) was 69% in favour, 31% opposed – accordingly, the opposed side (having moved the most votes) was declared the winner.

The participants did a magnificent job, and the debate was a model of its kind: rigorous, clear, respectful, and compelling. Not only did our debaters demonstrate the complexity and importance of the topic; they also modelled civil discourse on a contentious topic. The debate program generated an overwhelmingly positive response from the Researcher to Reader audience.

Acknowledgements:

We thank the organisers of the Researcher to Reader 2023 (www.R2RConf.com). Find more on the webpage: <https://r2rconf.com/r2r-conference-governance/>.

Malvika would also like to thank Arielle Bennett for sharing examples that were included in her speech.